

1 Phospholipase signaling during TE specification in the human embryo.

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification
9 of multiple components of the phospholipid signaling pathway as lineage commitment cooperating factor
10 in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. Relevant components included DGKK, ITPR2 and Pla2g4f.

11 Citations

12 1. van der Zanden, L.F., van Rooij, I.A., Feitz, W.F., Knight, J., Donders, A.R.T., Renkema, K.Y.,
13 Bongers, E.M., Vermeulen, S.H., Kiemeny, L.A., Veltman, J.A. and Arias-Vásquez, A., 2011. Common
14 variants in DGKK are strongly associated with risk of hypospadias. *Nature genetics*, 43(1), pp.48-50.